

MINDFUL BALANCE: IMPACTS OF YOGA PRACTICES THAT ENHANCE MENTAL HEALTH AMONG FEMALE COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to determine how Asana and Meditational practices affected college women students' mental health. Twenty female students from SRM Institute of science and Technology, Kattankulathur, were selected at random as the study's subjects. They were between the ages of 19 and 22. The selected participants were randomly divided into two groups, with group I performing Asana and Meditational practices (n=10) and group II serving as a control (n=10). For six weeks, members of Group I practiced Asana and Meditational practices on alternate days, attending one session per day. Group II took part in regular activities but did not receive any particular training. The data on a specific mental health criterion variable; The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale was used to evaluate it. The dependent-t test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were set at the 0.05 level of confidence for statistical analysis of the collected data. The statistical package SPSS- 22 version was used to analyze all of the data. It was determined that the group that combined Asana and Meditational practices had significantly better mental health than the control group, and that there were also significant differences between the experimental and control groups.

Key Words: Asana, Meditational Practices, Mental Wellbeing

1. Introduction:

Yoga is a way to teach the body, the mind (or intellect), and the inner spirit all at once. It is a centuries-old Indian practice and science. Both healthy and chronically ill individuals may benefit physically and psychologically from yoga. According to Harinath (2004), yoga asana are different ways to move and/or hold the body in different positions. We learn to recognize the connection between our physical, mental, and emotional levels through yoga practice (Joshi, 2004). Yoga is a very old practice. It is acknowledged as one of the Indian heritage's most significant and valuable gifts. The world today looks to Introduction 25 yoga as a solution to the various issues men face. According to Kumar & Arumugam (2018), yoga has never before attracted so much interest from people in so many different parts of the world. Yoga is a traditional form of mental and physical training. Masson Oural, a scholar from France, has said that yoga is the foundation of Indian culture always. According to Chandrashekar (1999), the various forms of yoga have had a significant impact on the spirit of modern India, resulting in its diversity and diversions. Numerous religious traditions have used Meditational since antiquity, frequently as a means of achieving enlightenment and self-realization. Asana for Meditational can be used to improve peace, perception, self-concept, and well-being while also reducing stress, anxiety, depression, and pain. According to Kasus (2009), research is underway to determine the potential health (psychological, neurological, and cardiovascular) and other effects of Meditational.

Positive mental health is defined as a state that "allows individuals to realize their abilities, cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively and fruitfully, and make a contribution to their community," according to the World Health Organization. Positive mental health is the "foundation for well-being and effective functioning for both the individual and the community." Another crucial aspect of good mental health is the capacity for long-lasting, mutually satisfying relationships (Ruth Tennant, 2007).

2. Purpose of the Study:

The study's objective was to determine the Impacts of Asana and Meditational practices affected college women students' mental health.

3. Material and Methods:

The purpose of this study was to determine the Impacts of Asana and Meditational practices affected college women students' mental health. Twenty female students from SRM Institute of science and Technology, Kattankulathur, The selected participants were randomly divided into two groups, with group I performing Asana and Meditational practices (n=10) and group II serving as a control (n=10). For six weeks, members of Group I practiced Asana and Meditational on alternate days, attending one session per day. Group II took part in regular activities but did not receive any particular training. The data on a specific mental health criterion variable; The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) was used to evaluate it. The WEMWBS is a mental health assessment that focuses solely on the positive aspects of mental health. WEMWBS has a 14-item scale with 5 response categories that are added together to give a single score. The items are all written in a positive way and address both the feeling and the functioning aspects of mental health, making the idea more understandable. The scale has been widely used to monitor, evaluate, and investigate the

factors that influence mental health both nationally and internationally." Sarah Stewart-Brown, Professor although there were no dropouts from the study, the subjects were free to withdraw their consent if they experienced any discomfort during the training. The subjects were medically examined by a qualified physician, and the results showed that they were suitable for the study. Before each training session, the subjects went through their respective program under the strict supervision of the investigator. Throughout the training, all of the participants were questioned about their health. None of the new participants reported an injury, but muscle soreness was reported in the first few weeks, but it went away later. By dividing the total number of training sessions by the number of sessions that were attended, the experimental group's attendance was determined to be 96.5 percent respectively. Jogging and stretching were part of a ten-minute warm-up exercise for the experimental group. The chosen asanas are tadasana (palm tree pose with raised hands), trikonasana (triangle pose), natrajasana (triangle pose), janusirsasana (head to knee pose), sasangasana (rabbit pose), dhanurasana (bow pose), virabhadrasana (warrior pose), yogamudra (forward bend), padmasana. The dependent-t test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were set at the 0.05 level of confidence for statistical analysis of the collected data. The statistical package SPSS-22 version was used to analyze all of the data.

4. Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Means and Dependent ‘T’-Test for the Pre and Post Tests on Mental Wellbeing of Experimental and Control Groups

Criterion Variables	Mean	Experimental Group	Control Group
Mental Wellbeing (Points)	Pre Test	27.54	26.32
	Post Test	38.02	27.84
	‘T’ Test	11.38*	1.60

*Significant at .05 level. (Table value required for significance at .05 level for ‘t’-test with df 9 is 2.26)

According to table I, the dependent-t-test values of mental wellbeing between the pre and post-test means of the experimental groups were greater than table value 2.26 with df 9 at 0.05 level of confidence, indicating that the experimental group outperformed the control group significantly in terms of mental wellbeing.

Computation of Analysis of Covariance:

The descriptive measures and the results of analysis of covariance on the criterion measures were given in the following tables.

Table 2: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance on Mental Wellbeing of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimenta I Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F
Mental wellbeing (Adjusted Post Mean)	38.24	27.95	BG	143.77	1	143.77	15.36*
			WG	159.12	17	9.34	

* Significant at 0.05 level. Table value for df 1, 17 was 4.45

According to the aforementioned table II, the adjusted mean scores for the experimental and control groups' mental health were 38.24 and 27.95, respectively. For the degrees of freedom 1 and 17 necessary for significance at the 0.05 level of confidence, the calculated F-ratio of 15.36 for the adjusted mean was higher than the table value of 4.45.

According to the study's findings, there was a substantial difference in mental wellness between the experimental and control groups.

5. Discussion on Findings:

Researchers Akhtar, Yardi, and Akhtar (2013) examined how yoga affected their ability to function and general well-being. An evaluation of the impact of yoga intervention on anxiety and subjective well-being was conducted by Jadhav and Havalappanavar in 2009. According to a 2012 study by Khalsa, Hickey-Schultz, Cohen, Steiner and Cope, yoga has positive effects on students' mental health. A study on the impact of yoga, pranayama, and Meditational on the mental health of female undergraduate medical students was undertaken by Lata in 2022. Elstad, (2020), examined how yoga affected students' mental health. In a single session, Park, (2020) investigated how various yoga styles alter psychological resources and emotional wellbeing. Given the preceding studies that influenced me, I set out to undertake this research. The findings indicate that, compared to the control group, college women students experienced a considerable increase in their mental health as a result of Asana and Meditational practices.

6. Conclusions:

- There was a considerable improvement in mental wellness among college women students as a result of the influence of Asana and Meditational practices.
- There was a substantial difference in the mental health of female college students between the experimental and control groups.
- However, none of the examined characteristics had significantly improved for the control group.

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